

WHAT ARE THE BEST LEG VEIN TREATMENTS?

Treating spider veins and varicose veins is important for many individuals looking for leg vein treatments to relieve these conditions. Varicose veins may seem to protrude from the skin and might be purplish or somewhat blue in shading. What's more, this venous condition may also lead to pain and heaviness in the legs. Spider veins may not bulge from the skin or cause pain, but they may be just as embarrassing due to their unsightly appearance. Depending on which condition is present, the [vein treatment](#) recommended by a vein specialist will likely vary.

Sclerotherapy:

While treating spider veins or more modest varicose veins, sclerotherapy might be suggested. This **vein treatment near me** involves the use of a chemical sclerosant that is used to irritate the vessel lining, causing the vein to shrink, collapse and eventually disappear entirely. The sclerosant is injected into the treatment area using a tiny needle by **vein doctor NJ**. The needle is so small that patients usually do not require a topical anesthetic, although one may be provided in some cases. A foam formulation is available at many clinics in addition to the traditional liquid formulation. The foam formulation allows for greater contact with the vessel lining as it displaces blood in the vein more effectively, and is more easily viewed on ultrasound.

Endovenous laser ablation:

Endovenous laser ablation is another **vein treatment Clifton** option but is often used to treat large varicose veins. This procedure involves the insertion of a laser fiber into a problem vein. The fiber is then slowly heated using low energy to destroy the problem vein. A local anesthetic may be provided for this treatment to help ensure patient comfort by the **vein specialist NJ**. Before undergoing this or any other treatment, patients should consult a specialist to discuss possible side effects.

Ambulatory phlebectomy:

Ambulatory phlebectomy is another leg [veins treatment Paramus](#) that helps patients suffering from varicose veins. With this treatment, tiny incisions are made along the problem vein so that vein hooks may be used to remove it. The incisions made are small enough that sutures are not required and the incisions typically heal without scarring. A local anesthetic is often provided when receiving this treatment as well to help ensure patient comfort.

There are several other minimally-invasive treatment options available at many vein clinics, and patients are always encouraged to explore all of their options so they make an informed treatment decision. A **vein doctor near me in woodland park** may recommend these or other treatments on a case-by-case basis to make sure that the patient receives the proper care.

Cost of leg vein treatments:

Treatment	cost
Sclerotherapy	Most procedures continue mid 15 minutes and 1 hour for cosmetic sclerotherapy. The normal costs for cosmetic sclerotherapy in NJ are \$300-\$1200
Endovenous laser ablation	Expenses for EVLT range from \$600 to \$3,000, depending upon the amount of the vein that should be dealt with. Protection may get part of the tab, nonetheless, if the varicose veins are painful.
Ambulatory phlebectomy	The cost of Endovenous Ablation may range between \$3,066 to \$5,758. People having high deductible health plans or without insurance can compare prices and save.